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"UNSPOKEN REGRETS"

In a quiet room where shadows play,
A daughter sits, the hours slip away.
Her heart feels heavy, a silent weight,
For moments lost, now wrapped in fate.

She watches the sun sink red and low,
Recalling laughter, the words unspoken.
How time passed by like fading melody,
While she chased dreams, as if thinking strongly.

But in the stillness, the truth unfolds,
In memories whispered, in tales retold.
The nights they could have spent together,
Now echo softly, like the ebbing tide.

She whispers "Father" through her tears,
"I yearn for the moments when I held you dear.
I wish I'd listened, shared more of me,
Before the time that you passed away."

Yet love persists, though with the limited days,
In every heartbeat, he's still with you.
For what is regret but a reminder fair,
We must value time together to show we care.

So as twilight settles, she gasps in the gloom,
Determined to honor him in every room.
With every step she takes, she'll carry his name,
A bond everlasting, a flickering flame.